

Deliverable 3.8: Invited lectures on specific topics update

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Workpackage:	3
Task:	3.3
Version:	1.0
Date:	29. 09. 2022

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports)
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web)

Executive summary

To minimize communication barriers between clinicians and scientists and to expand insights into the research landscape for students, reputed clinicians and scientific researchers will be invited to scientific meetings organized by BMC SAV to give keynote lectures on particular topics (e.g. colon, or pancreatic cancer, neuroendocrine tumours, advanced cell culture technologies, biomarkers, clinical trials). The lecture series started in October 2020 and has taken place continuously since then. Due to the coronavirus pandemic situation the lectures were given as online sessions. Until now eight invited lectures were realized (3 in 2020, 4 in 2021, 1 in 2022). Three more are planned until the end of 2022.

1 Description of work & main achievements

Reputed clinicians and scientific researchers have been defined to give keynote lectures during scientific online meetings organized by BMC SAV.

In October 2020, the lecture series started with an expert talk of Dr. Carrato from the Ramón y Cajal University Hospital Health Research Institute represented by Servicio Madrileño de Salud (SERMAS). In the following you find the speakers and the topic of the keynote lectures that have already taken place. More lectures are planned.

Invited lecture 1st – 14th October 2020:

Invited expert: Dr Alfredo Carrato

Topic of the lecture: **The treatment of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) in the clinical practice**

Number of participants: 54

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers: GA 857381

Challenges in exocrine pancreatic adenocarcinoma management

Alfredo Carrato MD, PhD
Ramón y Cajal University Hospital, IRYCIS, CIBERONC
Alcalá University. Madrid

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Invited lecture 2nd – 28th October 2020:

Invited expert: Dr Laura Garcia Bermejo

Topic of the lecture: **Molecular and Cellular mechanisms/biomarkers in PDAC**

Number of participants: 39

The slide features a decorative header with a green and blue wave pattern and the VISION logo. The main title is "Molecular and Cellular mechanisms/biomarkers in PDAC" in a bold, black font. Below the title is the speaker's name, "M. Laura García-Bermejo", followed by her affiliation: "Ramón y Cajal Health Research Institute (IRYCIS), Madrid, Spain". A URL for PDAC-AECC is provided: "http://pdacaecc.com". The bottom of the slide contains several logos: IRYCIS, Hospital Universitario Ramón y Cajal, Instituto de Salud Carlos III, FEDER (Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional), aecce (Asociación Española Contra el Cáncer), and COST.

Invited lecture 3rd – 11th November 2020:

Invited expert: Dr Julie Earl

Topic of the lecture: **Advances in familial pancreatic cancer**

Number of participants: 40

The slide has a dark purple background. At the top left is the IRYCIS logo, and at the top right is the Hospital Universitario Ramón y Cajal logo. In the center, there is a white icon of a presentation board with a line graph showing an upward trend. The main title "ADVANCES IN FAMILIAL PANCREATIC CANCER" is written in large, white, bold, uppercase letters. Below the title is the speaker's name, "Julie Earl", and her affiliation: "Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS) Madrid, Spain". At the bottom left is the VISION logo, and at the bottom right is the logo for the Spanish Familial Pancreatic Cancer Registry (PANGENFAM).

Invited lecture - 27th April 2021:

Invited expert: Thorsten Knoll

Topic of the lecture: **Microfluidic technologies and their applications in cell biology**

Number of participants: 31

Microfluidic technologies and their applications in cell biology

27th April 2021

Thorsten Knoll, Fraunhofer IBMT

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Invited lecture - 16th June 2021:

Invited expert: Pantelis Antonakis

Topic of the lecture: **Bariatric surgery and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease**

Number of participants: 29

Bariatric surgery and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD)

P. Antonakis MD, PhD

Athens Medical School, NKUA

within the VISION project for teaching purposes

16/6/2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Invited lecture - 4th November 2021:

Invited expert: Pavel Vodicka

Topic of the lecture: **Genomic instability, microenvironment and telomere homeostasis in colorectal cancer**

Number of participants: 40

Institute of Experimental Medicine, CAS

Genomic instability, microenvironment and telomere homeostasis in colorectal cancer

Pavel Vodička, M.D., PhD
Department of the Molecular Biology of Cancer

www.iem.cas.cz

VISION

Invited lecture 16th December 2021:

Invited expert: Núria Malats

Topic of the lecture: **Personalised Prevention of Pancreatic Cancer**

Number of participants: 19

Objetive:
Personalized Prevention of Pancreatic Cancer

Núria Malats, MD, MPH, PhD

Spanish National Cancer Research Centre (CNIO)

nmalats@cniio.es

Invited lecture – 15th June 2022:

Invited expert: Stefano Bonassi

Topic of the lecture: **New Perspectives in Clinical Trials**

Number of participants: 33

The exact topics of the lectures in the last nine months of the project will be determined during the next consortium meeting in October 2022. All upcoming keynote lectures in 2022 and 2023 will be realized as webinars.

Invited lectures with acceptance of speakers:

- 1) Invited expert: **Dr. Bruno Sainz, Jr., Ph.D.**, Cancer Stem Cells and Fibroinflammatory Tumor Microenvironment Group, Ramon y Cajal University Hospital (IRYCIS), Madrid, Spain

Topic of the lecture: Tumor-associated Macrophages: re-education with Lipid Nanoparticles to avoid Liver Metastasis in PDAC

Planned date of the lecture: 5th October 2022

- 2) Invited expert: **Dr. Joerg Schrader**, Department of Medicine, Klinikum Nordfriesland, Husum, Germany

Topic of the lecture: Translational research and pNET

Planned date of the lecture: November 2022

- 3) Invited expert: **Pantelis Hatzis, Ph.D.**, Researcher B in the Institute for Fundamental Biomedical Research and Head of Fleming Genomics Facility in the Biomedical Sciences Research Center 'Alexander Fleming' in Athens

Topic of the lecture: Next-generation sequencing in cancer research and diagnosis

Planned date of the lecture: 30th November 2022

- 4) Invited expert: **Carolina de la Pinta**, Radiation Oncologist, Ramon y Cajal University Hospital (IRYCIS), Madrid, Spain

Topic of the lecture: Radiomics and radiogenomics in cancer

Planned date of the lecture: 8th February 2023

2 Deviation from the workplan

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation the task „invited lectures“ was delayed in the first phase of the project. But the coordinator and all project partners worked together to compensate the delay by organizing more invited lectures in 2021 and 2022.

3 Conclusion

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation, invited lectures have been realized as online lectures. Invited experts agreed to the invitation. The lecture session started in October 2020 as webinar. The lectures, organized by BMC SAV, focus on project relevant topics (e.g. colon, or pancreatic cancer, neuroendocrine tumours, advanced cell culture technologies, biomarkers, clinical trials). Until now eight invited lectures were realized (3 in 2020, 4 in 2021, 1 in 2022). Three more are planned until the end of 2022.